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Tubig Liyang: A Legend from the Tausug Heritage of Talipao, Sulu

Aurizia Duhah Siraji
Associate Professor V
Sulu State College, Graduate Studies

Once upon a time in Talipao, one of the municipalities in the province of Sulu, the Irun family lived. Their lives are happy and simple. Planting crops is their livelihood. For them, those are not just a simple product, but it is life. That is why those crops are very important to them.

On the other hand, because their place is close to the mountains, the water in this area is poor. They have problem which is experiencing lack of water. This is the reason why planting is the main source of livelihood of the people here. They often only bath in water from cassava leaves and what they drink depends on rainwater and the stream. There were times when they got water from the other place using their horses as a transportation.

One morning they were surprised that something was missing from their crops. The day came when they had a hard time harvesting crops because something was pestering it. Until it happens again and again.

One day, Irun, a family man thought to watch out for who is pestering their crops. But he failed to know it. So, he decided to go home to their house. And his face shows sadness, tiredness and hunger. Because their suffering due to lack of water was added, there is pest in their crops. And when he came home, he earnestly prayed to Allah that it would rain so that someone could drink and that they could save water and have to use because every day in their area, water is always a problem. He could not bear what happened to their crops, so until the following days, he continued to observe. Soon he found out that it was a pig that was infesting and constantly consuming their crops.

One night while Irun is waiting for the pig, he heard someone's who speak, he quietly observed and looked everywhere, but there was no one. He was very surprised and scared because of what he saw, that the one who spoke was a pig with other little pigs. He was scared but he didn't leave because it was in his mind that his mission is to kill the pigs that consume their families crops. While the pigs were eating their crops, Apah Irun approached them stealthily and slowly. Using an antique sword, he hit the big pig.

"Success! You are making my family suffer more", Irun said. "We are having a hard time with water, and now we are also having a hard time with food because you are consuming our crops. You should die," Irun added.

Meanwhile, the group of pigs ran away, leaving the injured father pig behind. it screamed and begged. "Don't! Don't kill me. I'm not an ordinary pig. I come from a Jin. A Jin is an invisible being, who lives in the world. I live under this mountain. I am the leader of the others that you see earlier. Don't kill me because like you, my children and family need me too. I will take you to see the bottom of the mountain so that I can prove that what I said is true. It is a beautiful and there is water under which we live" explained by the pig.

"I know that one of your biggest problems is water, so when you let me live, you will have no problem with water. I will help you by guiding you the way to the water under the rocky mountain to solve your problem", the pig added.

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Because of Irun's desire to solve their problem with water. It didn't take long for the two to come to an agreement and Irun went with the pig under the mountain. When he came inside, Irun was shocked because there was water in front of him. "It's water! Irun shouted happily, and immediately drank the water. While Irun was having fun in his discovered water. He was very happy and surprised, that the pig turned into a human form, this is a handsome man.

Since you did not kill me," said the man. I apologize for what I had done. However, Irun also asked for forgiveness. Since then the two became friends. He happily took a tour to the beautiful houses that only appear in fairy tales. More than that, he was fed delicious food.

And in the afternoon, "I want to go home. But I will also return tomorrow to get some water", Irun said. "Your problem with water has a solution, you can take water from here even every day. And yes, you can take it whenever you want but just be careful around snakes or animals that bite. And I also want to tell you that this is the first and last time that you will see me", said the creature that changed into a human form.

Since then, the water has not been a problem for them. And people have been happy because of the discovery of water under the mountain that will support their daily life and their crops and they started to live a simple and normal life.

The water discovered under the mountain was called by the people Tubig Liyang. According to Apuh Jawadil, one of the elders living near the Mountain, Tubig Liyang is a very beautiful water under the mountain located in the Municipality of Talipao in the Province of Sulu. During the martial law, the people hide here to avoid bombs and cannons, which came from helicopters and brigades of soldiers. People say that Tubig Liyang not only provided drinking water and water for cooking, washing clothes, and bathing, but also helped save people's lives, as they hid there to escape bombs dropped from helicopters during martial law and other wars in the past, because it is concealed beneath Mount Talipao, where bullets could not penetrate.